
A Study to Assess the Psycho-Social Problems among Adolescent Students of Selected Pre-University Colleges

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Abstract: *Psycho-social problems have been identified as vital among adolescents at particular times when they enter the Pre-University. The various reasons were examination stress, personal and family life events. Psychosocial health problems are one of the hidden public health problems amongst the children and adolescents. Early identification, diagnosis and interventions are very important for preventing further complications. The aim of the study is to assess the psycho-social problems among adolescent students of selected Pre-University colleges. Taking 286 adolescent students from 3 Pre University Colleges of Belthangady Taluk of Dakshina Kannada district were selected through purposive sampling method. A set of structured questionnaire and Y-PSC was adopted to collect data, which were analyzed using SPSS software. Out of 286 adolescent students 25.5% were suffering with psychosocial dysfunction. Female students (17.5%) were more affected, compared to male students (8%). The psycho-social condition is significantly associated with demographic variable age and the type of abuse at home. More active measures like awareness and education programs for students, training for parents and teachers need to be given to take care of psychological and social health of adolescents.*

Key Words: *Psycho-social Problems, Adolescent, Public Health Problems, Awareness and Education Programmes.*

Introduction

Adolescence is the transitional stage of development between childhood and adulthood, representing the period of time during which a person experiences a variety of biological and emotional changes. Hall G S denoted this period as “Strom and Stress” and states “conflict at this developmental stage is normal” (Hall, G. S. 1904).

The term 'adolescence' is derived from the Latin word 'Adolescere' which means 'to grow to maturity'. Adolescence is a period of biosocial transition between childhood and adulthood. During this period the body grows very rapidly; as a result the movements, the voice etc., turn awkward. Adolescence period is fundamental biological, cognitive and social changes (Hill, J. 1983)

The World Health Organization (2003) defines adolescence as a period between ages 10 and 19. It is the formative period of life when maximum amount of physical, psychological and behavioural changes take place (Saldanha, D. 2007).

Adolescence is mainly affected by home and school environments. Schools play a vital role in the development of an adolescent, as they spend much time attending school, engaging in extracurricular activities, and completing scholastic work at home. School represents an institution that contributes to the overall educational and socialization processes, critical in personality development of an adolescent (Greenbaum, W. 1974). During this period, adolescents suffer from various forms of problems/dysfunctions and conflicts, which ultimately impair normal psychosocial development aggravating psychosocial dysfunction (Singh, S.B. and Pokharel, P.K. 2016).

Psycho-social problems refer to various problems of adolescents like behavioural problems, emotional problems, educational problems and social problems. Problems related to any or all the external activities of a person, which are observed directly, like behaviour that harms or threatens to harm others, lying, violation of rules etc, are behavioural problems. Emotional problems are the problems related to any of the particular feelings that characterize the state of mind. Educational problems include problems related to cognitive skills, teachers' and parental motivation in academic field, adjustment with the school etc. Social problems are the problems related to social environment such as social behaviour, social participation, peer influence and adjustment with family, society and religion (Mumthas, N.S. and Muhsina, M, 2014).

Rapid urbanization and modernization have exposed adolescents to changes in society. The resultant breakdown in family structure, excessive or minimal control confuses the adolescent and makes them especially vulnerable to maladaptive patterns of thinking and behaviour (Sadock, V.A., Sadock, B.J., Kaplan and Sadock 2000)

Need for the study

Globally, one out of 10 adolescents encounters at least one behavioural problem. Half of lifetime mental disorders begin before the age of 14 years, and 75% begin by the age 24 years (World health organization; 2001:39-4).

Sufficient data about the magnitude of the problem are very much essential for effective health care planning. Hence this study has been planned to assess prevalence and pattern of maladaptive behavioural and emotional problems among pre-university students.

Aim of the study

To assess the psycho-social problems among adolescent students of selected Pre-University colleges.

Objectives of the study

1. To assess the psychological and social problems of the adolescents.
2. To determine the family and college factors of adolescents.
3. To study the socio demographic information of the respondents.
4. To find out the association between the psychosocial problems with certain demographic variables, family and college related factors.

Materials and Methods

The study approval was taken from institutional ethics committee and written consent was obtained from both students and their parents. Non experimental descriptive research design with non probability purposive sampling method was adopted as a technique to collect the data. 286 students in the age group of 15 to 18 years, studying in three Pre-University colleges were selected as samples and the data was collected through structured questionnaire. Based on the proportion of psychosocial problem of 24.7% adolescents group, estimation error of 5% and level of significance 5% selected from three Pre-University colleges in Belthangady Taluk of Dakshina Kannada District.

The study instrument has 3 sections

1. Socio-demographic information.
2. Information regarding family and school.
3. Assessment of the emotional and behavioural problems using Youth-Paediatrics Checklist (Y-PSC) (Bhosale, S. et al., 2015).

The Y-PSC consists of 35 items that are rated as “Never,” “Sometimes,” or “Often” and scored 0, 1, and 2, respectively. The cut-off score for the Y-PSC is 30 or higher indicates psychological impairment.

The data collected was computerized and analyzed using SPSS software. Chi square test was used as the test for significance. P value less than 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results

Socio-demographic Information

Among 286 adolescents who participated in this study, 79% of them were of 17-18 years of age and 21% were in 15-16 years of age group. Female consist of 65.7% and male 34.3%. Majority 92.3% of the respondents were living in rural areas. 63.6% of the respondents represented from 1st year PU course and 36.4% from 2nd year PU course. Regarding religion 77.3% Hindus, 11.9% Muslims, 9.4% Christians and 1.4% Buddhists represented the study. 89.2% of the respondents were staying with parents. (Table No. 1)

Table 1: Distribution of Students According to Socio-Demographic Profile

Socio-demographic Factors	Number (%)
Gender (n=286)	
Male	34.3%
Female	65.7%
Age (n=286)	
15-16 years	21%
17-18 years	79%
Place of Residence (n=286)	
Village	92.3%
Town	7.7%
Staying Class (n=286)	
1 st year PU	63.6%
2 nd year PU	36.4%
Religion (n=286)	
Hindu	77.3%
Christian	9.4%
Buddhist	1.4%
Muslim	11.9%
Staying with (n=286)	
Parents	89.2%
Hostel/Pg/Relatives house	10.8%
Economic Status (n=286)	
Hardly sufficient	48.3%
Sufficient	50.3%
Surplus	1.4%

Information Related to Family and School

Among the respondents, 64% were living in nuclear families. 59.1% of the respondents' fathers educated up to primary school and 5.9% fathers were illiterate. 63.6% of mothers studied till primary school and 14.7% were illiterate. Majority 85.7% of families belong to BPL income category. Majority 91.6% have both the parents and they stay together. Only 8% of respondents faced verbal abuse at home and 14% from teachers in school. 17.1% of the respondents' fathers have a habit of abuse alcohol and 5.9% of the respondent's families other members were drinking. (Table 2)

Table 2: Distribution of Students According to Family and School Factors

Family Type	
Nuclear	64%
Extended	26.2%
Joint	9.8%
Family Size	
Up to 4	32.2%
More than 4	67.8%
Fathers' Education	
Primary	59.2%
High school	29%
PU and above	5.9%
Illiterate	5.9%
Mothers' Education	
Primary	63.7%
High school	19.2%
PU and above	2.4%
Illiterate	14.7%
Fathers' Occupation	
Not working/expired	8%
Farmer (agriculture)	8.8%
Cooli	34.6%
Business	3.8%
Skilled workers	9.4%

Mothers' Occupation	
Not working/expired	1%
Farmer (agriculture)	3.8%
Cooli	12.9%
House Wife	52.8%
Beedi Workers	29.4%
Economic Status	
APL	85.7%
BPL	14.3%
Type of Abuse Faced at Home	
Verbal	8%
No Abuse	92%
Alcoholism at Home	
Father	17.2%
Others	5.9%
None	76.9%
Academic Stress	
High	14.3%
Moderate	36.7%
Low	24.8%
No stress	24.1%
Types of Abuse at School	
Verbal	14%
Physical	0.3%
No abuse	85.7%

Psychosocial Problems and its Association with Related Demographic and Other Factors

Among the respondents 25.5% were facing psycho-social problems, (Figure 1) out of which 17.5% were female students and 8% were male students. 29.6% of respondents were of 17-18 years and 10% were from 15-16 years of age. 27.3% were represented from town areas, 25.4% represented from villages. The Buddhist religion 75% and 32.4% from Muslim religion were impaired with psychosocial problems. A total of 32.3% who were staying in hostel, paying guest and relative's house and 32.1% from joint families were

psychosocially impaired. 56.5% of the respondents who faced verbal abuse at home and 32.5% who faced verbal abuse at school were psychosocially impaired.

The psycho-social condition is significantly associated with demographic variable age and the P value is .002 and there is a significant association between the psycho-social problems and the type of abuse at home. (Table-3)

Figure 1: Psycho Social Impairment

Table 3: Statistical Score of Comparison of Psychosocial Impairment to Demographic Variables

Sl.No	Demographic Variable	Chi Square Value	Interpretation	P value
1.	Gender	.331	Not Significant	.565
2.	Age	9.627	Significant	.002
3.	Place of Residence	.038	Not Significant	.845
4.	Religion	10.655	Not Significant	.014
5.	Staying with	.829	Not Significant	.362
6.	Economic Status	7.120	Not Significant	.028
7.	Family Type	.731	Not Significant	.694
8.	Family Size	.520	Not Significant	.471
9.	Type of Abuse at Home	12.642	Significant	.000
10.	Alcohol Present at Family	.904	Not Significant	0.636
11.	Type of Abuse at School	4.210	Not Significant	.122

Discussion

The present study is done with the adolescent students who were studying in Pre University Course which shows 92.3% of the respondents were rural based and only 7.7% urban based. The selected colleges are situated in the rural area hence the representation is more from rural area. (Rajkumar E et al., 2015)

The study is represented by 77.3% of Hindus, 11.9% by Muslims, 9.4% Christian and 1.4% Buddhist. (Roy A. KS et al., 2018, Bhosale S, Singru SA and Khismatrao D, 2015).

The study results show that 50.3% families' income is sufficient and for 48.3% of families their income is hardly sufficient for their day today living. The respondents' families are with agricultural and coolie work, hence their income is sufficient or hardly sufficient for their living. (Banstola R.S, 2017).

This study shows that 64% live in Nuclear family and 26.2% live in extended family and rest 9.8% live in joint family. (Banstola R.S, 2017)

The present study shows that 67.8% families have more than four members in their family, whereas 32.2% have up to 4 members. In rural area even though more families are nuclear, they have more than two children. (Latiff L. A et al., 2017)

In this study 91.6% of respondents, both parents are living and they stay together. Rest 5.9% have single parent, both parents are not living or orphans and 2.4% of parents were separated or legally divorced. (Magklara et al., 2010).

The present study reveals that 25.5% of the adolescent respondents were facing psycho-social problems and 74.5% were not affected psychosocially. (Banstola R.S, 2017 and Sinha Roy A.K, et al., 2018).

Study results show that 29.6% of the age group of 17-18 years were impaired with psychosocial problems. Among the age group of 15-16 years 10% were impaired with psychosocial problems. There is a significant association between the age and the psychosocial conditions. (Timalsina M, Kafle M, and Timalsina R, 2018) and (Bhosale S, Singru S.A and Khismatrao D, 2015).

This study shows that 32.1% of respondents who live in joint family were psychosocially impaired. 25.3% from extended family and 24.6% from nuclear family were psychosocially impaired. There is no significance of association between type of family and psychosocial conditions. (Timalsina, M, Kafle, M and Timalsina, R. 2018)

The verbal abuse at home is faced by 8% of the respondent. While comparing it with psychosocial condition it is significantly associated, which means the children who face abuse are more likely to face psychosocial problems. 17.2% of the fathers were having a habit of drinking hence this also may be the reason for abuse.

Conclusion

In a present scenario the adolescent children are not openly communicating their problems with parents or teachers. They are more influenced by the media and try to practice whatever they see. Hence majority of the psycho-social problems among adolescents will remain unresolved. More

active measures like awareness and education programs for students, training for parents and teachers need to be given to take care of psychological and social health of adolescents. A trained student counsellor also is a great help to listen to adolescents and guide them in their difficulties. There should be a good study environment and student friendly programs to reduce problems and cope with psychosocial problems.

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